

THE ROLE OF MICROELEMENTS IN THE TREATMENT OF CHILDREN WITH COVID-19

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10664805>

Abstract:

The physiological significance of microelements is largely determined by their crucial role in the composition of the body's enzymatic systems. The optimal functioning of these systems depends on the regular intake of microelements from the environment. Deficiency or excess of microelements in the environment can lead to serious diseases. Considering the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, it is particularly important to note that the post-COVID condition in children may be associated with a deficit of specific microelements, potentially impacting their overall health. This underscores the need for additional attention to the status of microelements in the assessment and treatment of post-COVID effects in children.

Keywords: COVID-19, children, microelements, metabolism, treatment.

Relevance:

The COVID-19 pandemic has posed challenges to healthcare professionals in terms of early diagnosis and medical care for individuals with the new coronavirus infection. Scientific research is being conducted to study the clinical and epidemiological characteristics of the disease, develop new means of prevention and treatment. The potential for replenishing certain microelements in COVID-19 patients with the aim of early recovery is being discussed [1,2,3]. Systemic complications caused by the COVID-19 virus pose a serious threat to children's health, requiring comprehensive and effective treatment. In recent years, much attention has been paid to the role of microelements in supporting immunity and combating infections. Despite this, the impact of microelements on the course of COVID-19 in children remains insufficiently explored. The relevance of this study on the role of microelements in the treatment of children with COVID-19 is justified by the need for a deeper understanding of the influence of microelements on the immune system of a child's body in the context of this disease. Considering the peculiarities of the child's body and its response to the SARS-CoV-2 virus, elucidating the role of specific microelements can provide valuable information for optimizing treatment strategies and maintaining children's health during a pandemic. Such an approach can

contribute to the development of individualized therapeutic regimens, improving treatment outcomes, and reducing the negative consequences of the disease in children.

Research Objective:

The study aims to analyze the concentration of microelements, such as zinc, calcium, and phosphorus, in abrasive samples of the nasal and oropharyngeal mucosa in children who have had COVID-19.

Materials and Methods:

In this study, a group of 52 children under the age of 5 with a confirmed diagnosis of coronavirus infection (COVID-19) was observed. The diagnosis of COVID-19 was established by detecting RNA of SARS-CoV-2 using the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) method on samples taken from the nasopharynx and oropharynx.

Laboratory studies included a thorough analysis, including determining a complete blood count, biochemical indicators, and studying the microelement composition in the hair of children. The analysis of a complete blood count included the study of hematological parameters, including the leukocyte formula, erythrocytes, hemoglobin, and platelets.

Biochemical studies aimed to determine the levels of various biochemical markers, highlighting the body's condition in the context of COVID-19 infection. Simultaneously, an analysis of the microelement composition in the hair was conducted, providing a deeper understanding of the impact of microelements on the disease.

The control group consisted of 18 children who were practically healthy, providing a baseline for comparing changes caused by COVID-19.

Results:

The study revealed that among the examined children, just over half (53.8%) were organized and lived in urban areas. 69% of them had a pronounced predisposition to frequent illnesses. The symptoms of COVID-19 in these children manifested a clinical picture similar to acute respiratory viral infections (ARVI), including dry cough, sore throat, runny nose, and a temperature rising to 38°C.

Additional symptoms included the appearance of a rash in 11.5%, inflammation of the mucous membrane of the eyes in 7.7%, headaches in 9.6%, and signs of gastrointestinal disorders in 11.5% of children. The duration of COVID-19 was

on average 7-10 days. A follow-up examination of the health status of these children was conducted 2 months after the onset of the disease.

The analysis of microelement levels (zinc, calcium, and phosphorus) showed that the calcium level in patients in the early recovery period averaged 1.9 ± 0.04 mmol/L, significantly lower than in the control group of children (2.2 ± 0.05 mmol/L, $P < 0.01$). The zinc level in children who had COVID-19 during this period was on average 9.5 ± 1.0 mmol/L, which was 1.5 times lower than in the control group ($P < 0.01$). Similarly, the phosphorus level in patients averaged 1.18 ± 0.02 mmol/L, which also significantly differed from the control indicators (1.27 ± 0.01 mmol/L), ($P < 0.01$).

Conclusions:

The findings of the study indicate significant changes in microelement levels (calcium, zinc, and phosphorus) in children after COVID-19. A decrease in calcium, zinc, and phosphorus levels was observed, emphasizing the need for additional attention to the microelement status in the process of treatment and rehabilitation. These results support an individualized approach to caring for children after the illness, ensuring full recovery and minimizing potential consequences.

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